

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Bronchiolitis in the COVID era: Importance of prevention in these viruses

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Abstract

Bronchiolitis is a viral infection of the lower respiratory tract characterized by small airway obstruction, most often caused by respiratory syncytial virus (RSV). Bronchiolitis affects more than one-third of children in the first two years of life, and it is the most common cause of hospital admission in the first year of life. The absence of effective therapy against RSV infection makes prophylactic interventions and supportive care the best strategy to avoid complications of the disease.

In late December 2019, patients with viral pneumonia due to an unidentified microbial agent began to be reported in Wuhan, China. This disease outbreak, attributed to COVID-19, was declared pandemic by WHO in March 11th, 2020. Until a vaccine became available, a series of restrictions and preventive measures were taken worldwide to contain the spread of COVID-19. Although COVID-19 affects mostly elderly people, with children accounting for less than 5% of cases and rarely requiring hospitalization, indirect effects on this population have appeared, such as the containment of other respiratory viruses that affect this age group.

The main objective of this work is to show how COVID-19 preventive containment measures carried out in numerous countries may have influenced the bronchiolitis season. To this end, a literature search has been conducted addressing how the bronchiolitis season has changed since March 2020 in several countries, in relation to: prevalence of bronchiolitis-causing viruses, preventive measures directly affecting young children, modification of risk factors, and reorganization of the healthcare system.

Keywords: bronchiolitis, COVID-19, infection, prevention, VRS

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